

ISic3227

I.Sicily inscription 3227

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 836

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Diis Ma[nibus]

2. Domitiae · L(uci) · [---]

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (eng)

To the shades of the underworld. Domitia daughter of Lucius.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493972

EDR 139403

EDCS 22200391

Bibliography

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle

collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 76
Libertini, G 1930. Il Museo Biscari. Milan. At 75 no.161 ph

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3227. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4357314>